

Kinetics of Silver-catalysed Oxidation of Tl(I) by Persulphate

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The kinetics of silver-catalysed oxidation of Tl(I) by persulphate has been followed by estimating Tl(III) formed. The rate as usual is of first order in persulphate and silver ion each and independent of Tl(I). Salt effect is negative and exponential with a slope of -1 when $\log k$ vs. $\sqrt{\mu}$ is plotted. The inhibiting action of allyl and other compounds has been discussed. The anticatalytic action of Mn(II) in other persulphate oxidations has also been carried out.

Oxidation studies of Tl(I) by persulphate, whether kinetic or analytical, do not seem to have been made so far. The present work was undertaken to ascertain the mechanism of silver-catalysed reduction of persulphate in view of the existing varying opinions¹⁻³ Tl(II) was reported in most of the oxidations by Tl(III)⁴⁻⁶, analogous to As(IV) found by Kolthoff and co-workers⁹ and Daniels¹⁰. No such information is, however, available from the oxidation studies of Tl(I) as few such studies have been made¹¹. We also could not obtain such information because of the independence of the rate of reaction on the concentration of Tl(I) (*vide infra*).

Tl(I) is oxidised to Tl(III) by persulphate according to the stoichiometric equation:

The uncatalysed reaction is very slow, but in presence of Ag^+ it takes place at a measurable speed. The above stoichiometry was determined in presence of Ag^+ .

A preliminary study indicates that a minimum concentration of acid is essential to keep Tl(III) in solution or to check its hydrolysis. The situation is similar to that in the oxidation of Mn(II)¹² where MnO_2 is precipitated by the disproportionation of Mn(III) and the latter can be kept in stable solution only in 3.6 *M*- H_2SO_4 ¹³. Tl(III) easily hydrolyses¹⁴⁻¹⁵ in absence of acid to provide brown thallic oxide¹⁶ or thallic metahydroxide¹⁷.

1. Yost, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 48, 152.
2. Gupta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1950, 11, 320.
3. Fronaeus and Otto-Ostman, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 320.
4. Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 959; Duke and Bornog, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 1015.
5. Higginson *et al.*, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 29, 49.
6. Armstrong *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 60, 1861.
7. Arden and Plano, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3197.
8. Harkness and Halpern, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 3528.
9. Woods *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1964, 68, 1698.
10. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1473.
11. Duke and Borchers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5188.
12. Gupta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 178.
13. Gupta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1959, 35, 483.
14. Biederman, *Arkiv Kemi*, 1953, 5, 41.
15. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", 1932, V, pp. 469, 477.
16. Rabe, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 58, 23.
17. Lamy, *Compt. rend.*, 1862, 54, 1255; 1863, 58, 442.

The perchloric acid concentrations used were 0.1*M* and above for the concentrations of Tl(I) employed in this investigation.

The reaction is influenced by the variation in the ionic strength (*vide infra*) and hence perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate have been used to keep the ionic strength constant. In any single run, even in absence of these, the rate constants, are however, uniformly constant, indicating insignificant change in the ionic strength during the course of the reaction, but it is always better to keep ionic strength at some high value for comparing the results of different runs.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were either B.D.H. AnalaR or E. Merck G. R. quality. Water used was doubly distilled in Pyrex glass vessels. Potassium persulphate solution was freshly prepared by direct weighing and its concentration checked frequently by Ecardt's¹⁸ or arsenite¹⁹ method. Sodium perchlorate was prepared from perchloric acid by titration against a solution of NaOH to *pH* 7.0.

Calculated quantities of thallos nitrate, perchloric acid, and distilled water were taken in the reaction vessel, placed in a thermostat at 35°. Silver nitrate and persulphate were also separately thermostated. Calculated quantities were then added to the reaction vessel and the time noted after the half addition of silver nitrate. The total volume of the reaction mixture was 100 ml. After suitable intervals 5-ml aliquots of the reaction mixture were pipetted and Tl(III) estimated (*vide infra*).

Kinetic Procedure.—The aliquots (5 ml) were added to 0.05*N*-KI (10 ml) and the liberated iodine was titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution. Tl(III) forms thallic iodide which decomposes²⁰ to provide iodine.

Persulphate (0.01 to 0.05*M*) liberated insignificant amount (equivalent to not more than 0.03 ml of 0.01*N* thiosulphate) of iodine from such dilute solutions of iodide during the time interval taken in the titration. This was accounted for (different for different concentrations of persulphate) when calculating the volume of thiosulphate required for Tl(III). Silver ion did not interfere in this method. The amount of iodide was always in excess of the total equivalent concentrations of silver nitrate and thallos nitrate.

A few separate test determinations for Tl(III) solutions were also made by the described method. Tl(III) solution was prepared by treating thallos nitrate with excess of persulphate in presence of silver ions in perchloric acid solution. Excess of persulphate was destroyed by boiling and Ag(I) was precipitated with sodium chloride. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate furnished the expected iodometric (0.05*M*-KI) results.

The above modified iodometric method had to be used because none of the known

18. Ecardt, *Chem. News*, 1900, 81, 26.

19. Gupta and Ghosh, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 379.

20. Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", 1959, I, p. 676.

methods²¹⁻²⁴ were found suitable for determination of either persulphate, or Tl(I), or Tl(III). We did not attempt the permanganate method in view of the observations made by Berry²⁵ and Jilek and Luoss²⁶ that it was not instantaneous and was suitable for concentrated solutions of Tl(I). Recently a complexometric titration method for Tl(III) has been reported²⁷, but it could not be employed for want of details.

Some of the reaction mixtures, where Tl(I) was present more than Ag^+ , encountered a difficulty in titrations with thiosulphate. On addition of KI in such cases, a black precipitate was formed which did not appear to liberate iodine instantaneously as thallic iodide did. This difficulty disappeared, however, if more of silver nitrate solution was added to such aliquots before titration. The uncatalysed reaction also presented the same difficulty which could be removed by prior addition of suitable quantities of silver nitrate solution. An investigation of this problem revealed that thallic ion formed thallic tri-iodide^{28,29}, TlI_3 , with iodine solution in KI, analogous to KI_3 or KI_2 :

The tri-iodide does not afford iodine or does so very slowly. This complex tri-iodide holds the iodine very firmly unlike the behaviour of KI_3 . No organic solvent is able to extract iodine from this complex. If Ag^+ is present, this complex, however, decomposes or reacts according to the reaction:

and AgI_3 soon decomposes to furnish AgI and iodine. This has been verified by preparing thallic tri-iodide and titrating the iodine quantitatively in presence of Ag^+ , which otherwise cannot be done. The fact that there is no difficulty in titrations if Ag^+ concentration is equal to or more than that of Tl(I) indicates a reaction between TlI_3 and AgNO_3 . This in itself is, however, a problem and needs thorough investigation.

In some of the reactions, where the concentration of the persulphate was more than that of Tl(I), small quantities of a black precipitate appeared (not always) after the oxidation of Tl(I) was completed. This was found to be higher-valent oxides of silver³¹ or $\text{AgO}^{\cdot}$ ³² formed in the reaction:

This precipitate also could be kept in solution if the acid concentration in the reaction mixture was increased or if low concentrations of the reactants were employed.

21. Berry, *Analyst*, 1926, 51, 137; Swift and Garner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 113.

22. Issa and Issa, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 323.

23. Willard and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 36.

24. Zintl and Biesacker, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1926, 153, 276

25. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 304.

26. *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1929, 1, 83.

27. Talipov and Nigsi, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1964, 19, 697.

28. Sharpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2165.

29. Nichols, *J. pharm. chim.*, 1864, iv, 1, 25.

30. Well and Penfield, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1894, 47, 463.

31. Csanyi and Solymosi, *Acta Phys. Chim.*, 1959, 34.

32. Kirwin et al., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 1617.

Persulphate oxidations are reported to be photochemical³³ and very much susceptible to trace of impurities³⁴⁻³⁵. A preliminary study indicated that the reaction kinetics in dark was not different than that in the diffused light. The rate of the reaction did not change even if ordinary distilled water was used, though double-distilled water was always employed.

DISCUSSION

The reaction was found to be of first order with respect to persulphate and independent of concentrations of thalious nitrate and hydrogen ions. The rate has linear relationship with Ag^+ also. The reaction is, in fact, bimolecular (the slow step probably being termolecular), but has a first-order rate constant because the concentration of the catalyst, silver ion, remains constant. The first-order catalytic constants were calculated from the relation:

$$k_{\gamma} = \frac{2.303 \times \text{slope}}{[Ag^+]}$$

where the slope refers to that of the straight line, obtained by plotting the logarithm of the concentration of persulphate against time. Such time-order plots for different concentrations of silver ion are shown in Fig. 1. The order with respect to concentration³⁶ was also found to be very nearly one and the rate constant, k , was calculated from the relation:

$$\log(-dc/dt) = \log k + n \log C$$

where 'C' is the concentration of persulphate and $-dc/dt$ is the initial rate found by plane mirror method³⁷; n is the slope of the line obtained by plotting $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs. $\log C$ (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1. Effect of Ag^+ conc. at 35° .

$K_2S_2O_8=0.0797M$; $Tl(t)=0.005M$; $HClO_4=0.182M$; $NaClO_4=1.00M$.

Δ : $Ag^+=0.002M$; $\oplus$: $Ag^+=0.005M$; $\square$: $Ag^+=0.01M$;
 $\triangle$: $Ag^+=0.02M$; $\odot$: $Ag^+=0.025M$; $\times$: $Ag^+=0.03M$;
 $\bullet$: $Ag^+=0.04M$. Read " $2.5Ag^+$ " in place of Ag^+

33. Srivastava, Thesis, Allahabad Univ., 1955.

34. Srivastava, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1959, 202, 191.

35. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4770.

36. Letort, Thesis, Univ. Kanms, 1937; *J. chim. phys.*, 1937, 34, 206.

37. Latashev, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 47, 793.

FIG. 2. Determination of k_{γ} and order of the reaction from initial rates at 35° .

$Tl(t)=0.005M$; $Ag^+=0.005M$; $HClO_4=0.182M$;
 $NaClO_4=1.00M$.

Tables I and II show that there is little change in the catalytic constant though the concentration of the reactants is varied within wide limits.

TABLE I

First-order dependence on persulphate.

$[Tl(I)] = 0.01 M$. $[Ag^+] = 0.008 M$. $[HClO_4] = 0.182 M$. $[NaClO_4] = 1.00 M$.

$S_2O_8^{2-} (M)$	..	0.035	0.030	0.025	0.020	0.010	0.005
k_p (litres/mole/min)	..	0.426	0.426	0.422	0.426	0.427	0.427

TABLE II

Effect of varying the concentration of Ag^+ .

$[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.02 M$. $[Tl(I)] = 0.01 M$. $[HClO_4] = 0.182 M$. $[NaClO_4] = 1.00 M$.

$[Ag^+] (M)$	..	0.016	0.012	0.008	0.004	0.002	0.0008
$k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	..	6.823	5.100	3.447	1.706	0.847	0.341
k_p (l/mole/min.)	..	0.426	0.425	0.426	0.426	0.423	0.420

There was no change in the catalytic constant over the twenty-fold variation in the concentration of thallos nitrate from 0.002 to 0.04 M .

Ionic Strength.—The change in ionic strength was effected by varying the overall concentration of perchlorate. The rate of reaction decreased with the increase in the ionic strength.

TABLE III

$[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.02 M$, $[Ag^+] = 0.008 M$. $[Tl(I)] = 0.01 M$. $[HClO_4] = 0.182 M$.

$[NaClO_4] (M)$	..	0.00	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00
μ	..	0.270	0.522	0.772	1.022	1.272
k_p (l/mole/min.)	..	0.797	0.619	0.547	0.467	0.426

The general theory³⁸ of the influence of the ionic strength on the rate of reaction between ions is quantitatively applicable only when the reactant concentrations are below³⁹ 0.01 M for uni-univalent electrolyte. In order to work with lower concentrations of the reactants, the effect of ionic strength was studied at 50°. Table IV records such results. A plot of $\log k$ vs. $\sqrt{\mu}$ shows a straight line with a slope of 0.06 (Fig. 3).

TABLE IV

$[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.01 M$. $[Ag^+] = 0.002 M$. $[Tl(I)] = 0.005 M$.

$[HClO_4] (M)$	..	0.0	0.023	0.069	0.090	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.115
$[NaClO_4] (M)$	..	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.01	0.025	0.05	0.10
μ	..	0.040	0.068	0.109	0.132	0.155	0.165	0.160	0.205	0.250
k_p (l/mole/min.)	..	3.940	3.600	3.055	2.870	2.675	2.617	2.500	2.330	2.112

38. Sontehard, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, 10, 229.

39. Frost and Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", 1961, p 161.

It was not possible to work below these limits of concentration because at low acid concentration, thallic oxide was precipitated. For the first two reactions ($\mu=0.04$ and 0.068) aliquots were taken after shaking the reaction mixture on account of the formation of a suspension of thallic oxide. The slope of the line under these conditions is nearly one, conforming to a slow step of reaction between a positively charged ion and two negatively charged ions, as explained later. Such a conclusion is somewhat doubtful in view of the ionic strength not being in the required range.

FIG. 3. Effect of ionic strength at 50° .
 $K_2S_2O_8=0.00485M$; $Tl(t)=0.005M$; $Ag^+=0.005M$;
 $HClO_4=0.162M$.
 Ionic strength varied with the help of $NaClO_4$.

FIG. 4. Effect of changing the acid concentration (ionic strength) at 35° .
 $K_2S_2O_8=0.0097M$; $Tl(t)=0.005M$; $Ag^+=0.008M$.

Effect of Perchloric and Sulphuric Acids.—The rate is independent of the hydrogen-ion concentration. The decreased rate in presence of the acid is due to the increase in the ionic strength. Table V records these results.

TABLE V

Effect of hydrogen ion.

$$[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.02M. [Tl(t)] = 0.01M.$$

A. In absence of perchlorate. $[Ag^+] = 0.008M$

$[HClO_4] (M)$	..	0.108	0.210	0.320	0.424	0.530	1.060	2.120	2.650	3.180	3.710
μ	..	0.198	0.300	0.410	0.514	0.620	1.150	2.210	2.740	3.270	3.800
k_γ (l/mole/min.)	..	0.960	0.822	0.702	0.670	0.612	..	0.355	0.297	0.234	0.181

B. In presence of perchlorate= $1.00M$. $[Ag^+] = 0.02M$.

$[HClO_4] (M)$	..	0.182	0.360	0.455	0.546	0.730	0.910
μ	..	1.27	1.45	1.54	1.63	1.82	2.00
k_γ (l/mole/min.)	..	0.425	0.422	0.417	0.405	0.362	0.362

All these results could be explained on the basis of negative exponential effect of the ionic strength. Plots of Tables V (A and B) and VI are shown in Fig. 4.

The hydrogen ion has little effect also in the oxidations of Ce(III)^{40} , Cr(III)^1 , Mn(II)^{11} , and VO(II)^{41} ions. The present reaction therefore is similar in all respects to the oxidation of most of the inorganic compounds by persulphate.

In some of the experiments sulphuric acid was employed. The results are similar, provided that the contribution to the ionic strength from sulphuric acid is taken into account. Table VI shows these results.

TABLE VI

Effect of sulphuric acid.

$$[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = 0.02M. \quad [\text{Tl(I)}] = 0.01M. \quad [\text{Ag}^+] = 0.008M.$$

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] (M)$	0.05	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.25	1.75	2.50
k_T (1/mole/min.)	0.862	0.647	0.545	0.460	0.425	0.327	0.287

Influence of Sulphate and Other Ions.—As sulphate or bisulphate ion is a reaction product, its concentration increases during a run. The lack of any significant deviation of the first-order rate constants during an experiment therefore indicates that the reaction rate is independent of sulphate concentration. The only effect of adding potassium sulphate or bisulphate is that of increasing the ionic strength and consequent decrease in the rate. If high concentration of sodium perchlorate is used to keep the ionic strength constant, there is, however, no effect of the added sulphate ions. Other substances employed and found without any effect were potassium nitrate, sodium nitrate, cobalt nitrate, copper sulphate, and manganous sulphate. In case of manganous sulphate, a manganese dioxide suspension was obtained, but this did not interfere with the reaction, nor with the method of estimation of Tl(III). Manganese dioxide also liberates iodine, as Tl(III) does, affording the rate constants exactly similar to the ones obtained for Tl(I) alone. This lends support to the fact that the mechanism of the reaction is very similar to the one supposed in the oxidation of Mn(II)^{11} . Whatever reactive intermediate is formed from persulphate and silver ions, it can oxidise both Mn(II) and Tl(I) together. The rate of the reaction is not at all changed because MnO_2 and Tl(III) both are determined by the method adopted for following the kinetics. This actually provides the rate of decrease in the concentration of persulphate. If one adopts a method to determine exclusively Tl(III), the rate of formation of the latter, however, would no longer be equal to the rate of decrease of persulphate.

Inhibition by Allyl and Other Compounds.—A few drops of allyl chloride, added to the reaction mixture and shaken, completely checked oxidation of Tl(I), but the allylchloride was polymerised⁴²⁻⁴³ and there was decrease in the concentration of persulphate. A similar behaviour was found in presence of acetic, oxalic, citric, and tartaric acids, sodium salts of these acids, glycerine, glycol, ethyl acetate, methanol, acetone, glycine, and dioxane. All these compounds were slowly oxidised by persulphate at different rates [but more quickly than the separate oxidation of Tl(I) alone] and Tl(I) was not oxidised. Fig. 5 shows such a phenomenon with oxalate ion and arsenious acid. Two lines with different slopes

40. Cone, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 78.41. Yost and Clausen, *ibid.*, 1931, **53**, 3349.42. Bacon, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **42**, 140.43. Morgan, *ibid.*, 1946, **42**, 169.

are obtained. One represents the oxidation of oxalate or arsenious acid and the other that of Tl(I) or Mn(II). The experiments with Mn(II) were also carried out because of its similarity of behaviour to that of Tl(I) in persulphate oxidation. The zero time for the second part of the reaction was counted from the time when the decrease in the concentration of the persulphate was equal to the oxalate initially taken. Persulphate was always in excess. In presence of the above mentioned substances, Tl(III) is not formed, not because Tl(I) is not oxidised but because Tl(III) formed is reduced by the oxidation products of the above mentioned substances. The results of the following few tests substantiate this conclusion. Tl(III) was allowed to remain in contact separately with oxalate, citrate, tartrate, acetate, glycerol, glycol, and glycine and no change in the concentration of Tl(III) was found even in an hour. If these substances are first treated with persulphate-silver ions mixture and then mixed with Tl(III), the latter was immediately reduced to Tl(I).

FIG. 5. Peroxodisulphate (oxidation of (A) oxalate (⊙) and Mn(II) (X); (B) arsenious acid(⊕) and Mn(II) (Δ); (C) oxalate (●) and Tl(I) (□)).

[A] : $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.0194M$; $Na_2C_2O_4 = 0.001M$; $Mn(II) = 0.01M$; $Ag^+ = 0.002M$; $HClO_4 = 0.182M$.

[B] : $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.0097M$; $H_3AsO_3 = 0.01M$; $Mn(II) = 0.01M$; $Ag^+ = 0.002M$; $HClO_4 = 0.182M$.

[C] : $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.0194M$; $Na_2C_2O_4 = 0.01M$; $Tl(I) = 0.005M$; $Ag^+ = 0.002M$; $HClO_4 = 0.182M$.

It is therefore concluded that Tl(I) is definitely oxidised to Tl(III), but the latter is subsequently reduced back to Tl(I) by the oxidation products of citrate, oxalate, etc. If the kinetics is followed by estimating Tl(III), the reaction would seem to be checked, but if persulphate ion is estimated iodometrically⁴⁴, the rate on the other hand would appear to be faster. Kinetics of silver-catalysed persulphate oxidations of oxalate, tartrate, acetate, etc. in absence and presence of Tl(I) were also carried out. The rates were identical

in the two cases. This obviously points to the fact that oxalate, tartrate, etc. and Tl(I) are oxidised simultaneously in a fast step. Tl(III) so formed is subsequently reduced by the oxidation products of oxalate, tartrate, etc. and the presence of Tl(I) does not affect the rate.

A similar situation exists in the oxidation of Mn(II) in presence of oxalate or arsenious acid or *vice versa*. Mn(II) and acid, both, are oxidised. Mn(III) is formed, which in high acid medium (HClO₄) immediately oxidises oxalate or arsenious acid and is itself reduced back to Mn(II). The reaction mixture does yield a stable red colour in presence of fluoride ions. Mn(III) is known⁴⁵ to form a stable red complex with fluoride ions and this observation strongly suggests that Mn(II) is definitely oxidised by persulphate even in presence of oxalate or arsenious acid.

Another important fact, noticed in this connection and reported earlier⁴⁶ also, is that the reduction of persulphate by different substances takes place with different rates. In case of Mn(II), Ce(III), VO²⁺, etc., the rate constant has been found to be 0.3–0.4 M⁻¹ min⁻¹ at 25°. It varies from 20 to 35 M⁻¹ min⁻¹ for oxidations of oxalate, citrate, formate, and arsenious acid. This roughly divides the oxidations in two classes. In line with this, we find that oxidations^{46,47} of oxalate, arsenious acid, citrate⁴⁸, pyruvate⁴⁹, etc. are strongly antioctalysed by Mn(II) and influenced by hydrogen ion in a complicated way, whereas the other class of oxidations is free from these influences. Since the rate of all these oxidations depends on the concentrations of persulphate and silver ions, it appears that the rate-determining step involves slightly different species of silver (I) in the two types of oxidations.

Energy and Entropy of Activation.—The variation of the rate constant with temperature is shown in Table VII. A plot of log k_p vs. $1/T$ shows a straight line. The energy of activation was found to be 12320 cal./mole from the slope of the line in the temperature range studied. The entropy of activation was found to be –22.7 e.s.u.

TABLE VII

Rate at different temperatures.

[S₂O₈²⁻]=0.02M. [Tl(I)]=0.01M. [Ag⁺]=0.008M. [HClO₄]=0.182M. [NaClO₄]=1.00M.

Temp.	36°	40°	45°	50°
k_p (l/mole/min.)	0.426	0.612	0.947	1.127

The Uncatalysed Reaction.—This reaction, though very slow, was studied at the above four temperatures (Table VIII). Hydrogen ion was found to increase the rate. These rate constants could also be calculated by plotting the experimental rate constants (not the catalytic constants) of the catalysed reaction against different concentrations of silver ion at the four temperatures. Straight lines are obtained as shown in Fig. 6. The intercept on the rate-constant axis at zero silver-ion concentration furnishes the rate of uncatalysed reaction. The measurement of the intercept with accuracy was possible by replotting the experimental points with a magnified scale only for lower concentrations of silver ion. Table VIII shows a comparison of the experimental and graphical values.

45. Bradley and Praagh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1824.

46. Gupta and Nigam, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 125.

47. Misra and Gupta, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1959, 32, 1806.

48. Gupta and Misra, unpublished work.

TABLE VIII

$[\text{NaClO}_4]=1.00M$; other conditions same as in Table VII.

Temp.	35°	40°	45°	50°
Expt. $k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	..	0.020	5.905	8.723
Graphical $k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.67	0.00	5.60	8.40
k (for $[\text{Ag}^+]=$ $0.008 M) \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	341.2	490.0	677.3	008.1

The rate constants for the catalysed reaction are also shown for the sake of comparison. The catalysed reaction is thus at least 500 times faster than the uncatalysed reaction at 35° and the latter may be neglected.

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8=0.0097M$
 $\text{Tl(I)}=0.005M$
 $\text{NaClO}_4=1.0M$
 $\text{HClO}_4=0.182M$

FIG. 6. Variation of (k) with the change in the conc. of Ag^+ at dif. temp. and (k) for uncatalysed reaction from the intercept.

Reaction between Persulphate and Silver Ion.—This reaction was followed in perchloric acid medium of the same strength as was used for the oxidation of Tl(I) . The kinetics was followed by estimating the persulphate iodometrically⁴⁴. Ag(II) or Ag(III) formed⁴⁶ oxidises water, the medium itself, since no reducing substance is present. If the concentrations of the reactants are high, a concentration of Ag(II) or Ag(III) is, however, built up, resulting in higher estimated values of persulphate. It appears that the oxidation of water by higher-valent silver is not as fast as the formation of the latter. At lower concentrations of the reactants, the rate was very similar as found in the case of the oxidation of Tl(I) . Obviously, the mechanism in the two cases is the same and the oxidation of Tl(I) takes place in a fast step.

Mechanism

Any consideration of the mechanism has to take into account the following facts, found earlier or reported in this communication:

- (1) The present reaction is of first order with respect to persulphate and independent of the concentration of Tl(I). The rate increases in a first-order way with increase in the concentration of silver ions.
- (2) Hydrogen, sulphate, and bisulphate ions have no influence on the rate. Acid-base equilibrium does not seem to be involved in this mechanism.
- (3) Manganous or other ions have no influence.
- (4) Salt effect is negative and a plot of $\log k_\gamma$ vs. $\sqrt{\mu}$ provides a straight line with a slope of -1 .

The rate-determining step therefore involves the persulphate ion or any species thereof and Ag(I). The latter also may exist in different forms in presence of different substrates. It might be simple Ag^+ in oxidations of Mn(II), Tl(I), Ce(III), etc. and a complex ion in oxidations of oxalate, citrate, arsenite, etc. The two types of oxidations can be explained in this way.

The existence of higher-valent silver as an intermediate in silver-ion catalysed persulphate oxidations is now well established and the probable mechanism for the present reaction appears to be as follows:

Reaction (iii) might alternatively occur in two fast steps without affecting the kinetics. From the above mechanism,

$$\begin{aligned} -dc/dt &= -\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/dt = k_2[\text{SO}_4^-]^2 \cdot [\text{Ag}^+] \\ &= k_2 \cdot K [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \cdot [\text{Ag}^+] \\ &= k_\gamma [\text{Ag}^+] \cdot [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \\ &= k [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \end{aligned}$$

Experimentally determined rate constant, k , is equal to $k_2 \cdot K \cdot [\text{Ag}^+]$ or $k_\gamma [\text{Ag}^+]$ and from this the catalytic constant, k_γ , can be calculated. K is small because the equilibrium concentration of SO_4^- is low.

A termolecular slow step, though generally unlikely, might occur particularly when preceded by a rapid equilibrium. The salt effect for the three types of ions (one positive and

two negative can be calculated* from the Debye-Hückel equation and the concerned line would have a slope of -1 ; the experimental value is -0.97 . In certain oxidations** rate of half order in persulphate has been reported. It is not unlikely that under certain conditions the step (ii) may become

leading to a half-order dependence on persulphate. The above mechanism with a slight modification can explain the other types of oxidations also. For the oxidation of oxalate, the rate-determining step may be:

preceded by the equilibrium:

The much reported⁵¹⁻⁵³ step of the mechanism:

cannot be included in the proposed mechanism because this slow step would not lead to a fast reaction in presence of Ag^+ unless persulphate is consumed again in atleast one subsequent step, resulting in fractional orders or there is a chain reaction involving a rate dependence on the concentration of Tl(I) . None of the above such trends have been noticed in the present reaction and hence the rate-determining step in all probability is preceded by a rapid equilibrium.

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* For a reaction among three ionic species, A, B, and C

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \log f_A f_B / f^*$$

(where f 's are the activity coefficients of the reactants and f^* , that of the activated complex)

$$= \log k_0 + \log f_A + \log f_B + \log f_C - \log f^*$$

$$= \log k_0 - Q\sqrt{\mu} [Z_A^2 + Z_B^2 + Z_C^2 - (Z_A + Z_B + Z_C)^2]$$

$$= \log k_0 + 2Q\sqrt{\mu} (Z_A Z_B + Z_A Z_C + Z_B Z_C)$$

(where Z 's are the charges and Q is constant ≈ 0.51 ; μ is ionic strength).

If Z_A is -1 , Z_B is -1 , and Z_C is $+1$

$$\log k = \log k_0 + 1.02\sqrt{\mu} (-1)$$

$$= \log k_0 - 1.02\sqrt{\mu}.$$

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